

DAMAGE EVOLUTION IN CARBON FIBER VINYL ESTER MARINE COMPOSITES AND SEA WATER EFFECTS

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on comparing the deformation behavior of matrix dominated samples having $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ orientation with the fiber dominated samples of $[0/90]_{2S}$. In order to evaluate the effects of long term exposure to sea water, a time aged (dry) and saturated samples are subjected to controlled rate of strain monotonic loading with several unload-reload loops to evaluate the accumulated plastic strain (damage) as a function of stress amplitude. Damage is quantified using surface strain variations along the gage length of a deforming sample using a high resolution three-dimensional digital imaging correlation system. The surface deformation data obtained from 3D-DIC is then considered synergistically with the variation of microstructural features obtained from high-resolution X-ray micro-tomography. The experimental techniques developed for this study are then utilized to evaluate the effect of sea environment on the damage behavior of marine composites for tensile monotonic loading conditions. The results from this study will also be extremely valuable for developing future material systems and loading scenarios in fatigue conditions to exploit a microstructure that can minimize accumulation of damage from repeated loading, blast, and impact conditions under harsh naval environment. In order to extend the observations from coupon based mechanical tests of fiber reinforced polymer composites, towards the design and application of large ship structures, it is important to consider the effect of the physical specimen size. Various sizes of CF/VE composite specimens are implemented in this study having a nominal thickness of 2.8 mm. The length scales influencing the damage accumulation leading to eventual failure of both matrix and fiber dominated samples are determined providing important new insight on the mechanical behavior of carbon fiber based polymer composites and associated failure mechanism as a function of sea water exposure.

1 INTRODUCTION

Marine composites are subjected to sea environment and thus are exposed to sea water for sustained periods of time. Due to the recent weather changes, naval ships now have access to cold regions for longer durations and thus understanding the coupled effects of temperature and sea water are also important on the static, fatigue, and fracture behavior of fiber reinforced polymer composites. This paper presents a fundamental study on the damage evolution of composite materials being considered by US Navy made of T700 based carbon fiber fabric (12k tows and plane weave) and vinyl ester resin (Derakane 510A) using VARTM process. Large panels of approximately 1.5 m x 1.5 m are manufactured and coupon samples are obtained from various orientations. For this study, focus will be on comparing the deformation behavior of matrix dominated samples having $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ orientation with the fiber dominated samples of $[0/90]_{2S}$. To evaluate the effects of long term exposure to sea water, coupon samples are soaked at 40 °C for extended period of time till full saturation state through the diffusion process is reached, confirmed by periodic evaluation of weight gain with square root of time.

A good overview of size effects in the testing of fiber reinforced polymer materials is given by Wisnom and Sutherland [1,2]. Wisnom's work reported that unidirectional polymer composite specimens of AS4 carbon /epoxy showed a decrease in tensile strength with increasing specimen size. Their sizes varied from 12.5-50 mm wide and 125-500 mm long. The epoxy based system was lay-up and cured on the site. The study further indicated that transverse cracking and edge delamination caused premature failure in FRP composites [3]. Size effect on the strength of unidirectional carbon

fiber reinforced composites was evaluated experimentally and it showed that CFRP strength was decreased while the size increased. Microscopic and numerical observation suggested that localized damage leads to the final failure of CFRP composites [4]. Reduction in tensile failure and flexural strength (4-point bending tests) of glass fiber-epoxy with increasing specimen size were reported [5]. The capabilities of X-ray computed laminography and tomography technique have been demonstrated for evaluating the micro-mechanisms leading to failure in pre-preg carbon fiber epoxy unidirectional composite samples [6,7]. The method of 3D DIC has been widely used in many applications ranging from metal surface deformation to crack growth fracture mechanics. Although successfully used in mechanical testing of fiber reinforced polymer over many years, strain gage and extensometer based data are still limited to small sampling location for the measured strain data, thus missing strain localizations. Failure development of carbon fiber composites monitored by the DIC technique can be useful to identify the potential occurrence of strain localization and its role in the observed deformation and failure response. The purpose of this study is twofold: to examine CF/VE specimen size effects based on mechanical testing, and to use DIC as well as X-ray and neutron tomography to evaluate damage evolution on the surface and deep inside the sample non-invasively which then will also be useful to interpret data associated with the specimen size effects.

2 MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

2.1 Material

The CF/VE composite facing consisted of stitch-bonded fabric of carbon fiber tows embedded in vinyl ester resin. Each carbon tow consisted of 12k Toray's Torayca T700 individual fibers and the facing was prepared from the impregnation of equi-biaxial fabric. The carbon stitch fabric used a vinyl ester compatible sizing, designated as LT650-C10-R2VE, supplied by the Devold AMT AS, Sweden. The matrix resin was Dow Chemical's Derakane 510A-40, a brominated vinyl ester, formulated for the VARTM process. The bromination imparts a fire-resistant property to the composite. Vinyl ester has a higher fracture strain than the typical polyesters, and hence produces composites with superior mechanical strength and impact resistance. The fiber volume was found to be 58% by the areal density method and includes 2.2% weight of polyester stitch fiber. Four plies of Devold LT650 fabric were stacked symmetrically to have 2.5 mm nominal thickness. VARTM approach was implemented to make large panels of the composites and sandwich structures using facilities at the Composites Fabrication Laboratory at North Carolina A&T University using established protocols [8]. CF/VE facing panel consists of four plies of Devold LT 650 fabric and vinyl ester resin as shown in Figure 1. Specimen were prepared at differently orientation to obtain fiber and matrix dominated specimen $[0/90]_{2S}$ and $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ respectively as demonstrated schematically in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Carbon fiber reinforced vinyl ester (CF/VE) composites prepared at different orientations (fiber and matrix dominated specimen consisting of four cross-stitch plies of *Devold LT 650* 12k Toray's Torayca T700 carbon fiber tow) and vinyl ester resin.

2.2 Mechanical testing and Digital Image Correlation (DIC)

All tensile tests were performed at a constant crosshead rate of 0.1 mm/min at room temperature in air. At least twenty five millimeter long tabs and a suitable adhesive were selected in order to minimize effect of gripping on mechanical behavior and avoid failures within tab section. An extensometer was used to record strain data if applicable. It was confirmed that DIC technique showed akin strain data when comparing with extensometer data. The DIC system (commercial available, VIC-3D) uses dual-cameras to measure the shape of an object, displacements, and full-field strains in three dimensions. The basic method tracks the gray value pattern in small pixel neighborhoods called subsets during deformation. Experimental set-up is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Experimental set-up for a tensile test using a servo-hydraulic loading system, coupled with DIC system for obtaining strain data on the specimen surface.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mechanical and DIC results

Fiber and matrix dominated specimens, $[0/90]_{2S}$ and $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ respectively, showed similar stress-strain behavior for all sample sizes considered in this study. No damage was found until catastrophic failure as shown in Figure 3a for fiber dominated specimens corresponding to $[0/90]_{2S}$ lay-up. The strain information reported in these stress-strain curves was obtained using DIC technique. Figure 3b shows the deformation behavior for a matrix dominated specimen, showing significant damage accumulation beyond 80 MPa axial stress. Typical mechanical properties of fiber and matrix dominated carbon fiber reinforced vinyl ester composites can be found in Table 1. More details of CF/VE mechanical properties at different orientations are reported by Siriruk and Penumadu [14,15].

Figure 3: Typical stress-strain behavior of (a) fiber [0/90]_{2S} and (b) matrix [±45]_{2S} dominated CF/VE sample dimensioned 300 mm long by 25mm wide.

Property	
Longitudinal modulus [0/90] _{2S}	60 GPa
Longitudinal modulus [±45] _{2S}	15 GPa
Ultimate strength [0/90] _{2S}	1000 MPa
Ultimate strength [±45] _{2S}	120 MPa

Table 1: Typical material properties of CF/VE composites.

CF/VE specimen sizes were scaled up 2 and 3 times (12.5 by 100 mm, 25 by 200 mm, and 25 by 300 mm) the baseline case keeping constant thickness using the same four cross stitched plies (2.8 mm), due to fabrication process and for comparison purpose. The large size of both fiber and matrix dominated specimen showed similar strength and moduli as summarized in Figure 4. More detail can be found in Woracek et al. [12].

Figure 4: Summary of property results for scaled CF/VE samples.

Figure 5 and Figure 8 depict characteristic fiber and matrix CF/VE specimen of damage evolution respectively using DIC principal strains at different stress levels specifically. It is possible to observe the damage evolution of CF/VE [±45]_{2s} and as expected, the discrepancy of strain distribution is larger for stress level at 100 MPa. Corresponding to 20 to 80 MPa possibly within elastic range of CF/VE [±45]_{2s}, damage evolution in sense of strain data is very well distributed within specimen gage length. Increasing the stress level to 100 MPa evidently grows the transverse shear band. However, a different damage evolution is observed on fiber dominated CF/VE [0/90]_{2s} showing few localizations since early stress stage at 200 MPa identified by DIC technique. With stress increase from 200 MPa to 1000 MPa, it shows possible cracks due to fiber splitting grow at several locations leading to the failure. This is important in correlating these results with X-ray and Neutron in-situ observation.

CF/VE samples were subjected to controlled rate of strain loading with 10 load-unload loops to evaluate accumulated plastic strain in Figure 6. Damage accumulation shown in Figure 7 can be quantified using high resolution X-ray tomography at high strain location. More results will be included during presentation.

Figure 5: Deformation variation of matrix dominated CF/VE using major principal strains at various specific stress levels

Figure 6: Typical load-unload behavior of $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ CF/VE

Figure 7: Damage evolution of matrix dominated CF/VE subjected to tensile load-unload varying from first cycle to 10th cycle

Figure 8: Deformation variation of fiber dominated CF/VE using major principal strains at various specific stress levels.

Based on the DIC results, failure of the different CF/VE sample sizes are caused by strain localization and defects such that size effects are not significant. Since strength and moduli are controlled by defects, especially voids and manufacturing damage during specimen preparation, it is crucial to make sure that good manufacturing quality of test specimens is achieved in production. The fundamental question of why certain zones lead to large accumulation of strain localization for the carbon fiber composites was further explored by attempting limited in situ tomography study using x-rays and neutrons.

3.2 X-ray and Neutron tomography

X-ray tomography has been reported previously [11-13]. However, using the Neutron based tomography data [14], we attempt to discern differences between dry samples and previously saturated (wet) samples, which is of interest because the material is utilized in boat/ship and aircraft structures and therefore subjected to environmental degradation by water diffusion on long time scales. Experiments conducted at HZB can help to understand the structural properties and why the material shows significant degradation in cyclic fatigue and fracture behavior when saturated with water compared to dry condition [15]. It is suspected that water conglomerates in voids, micro-capillary pores at the interface between carbon fiber bundles and resin matrix, and/or within the free volume of the polymer matrix and incompressibility of water leads to premature failure of bonding between fiber and matrix material and/or delaminations between layers of resin impregnated stich bonded fabric.

The reconstructed tomography images Figure 9 show individual fiber bundles within the sample volume and how they are embedded in the resin matrix. After applying mechanical stress, fractured fiber bundles and cracks in the resin can be observed. Initial analysis shows that for dry samples the damage was localized/concentrated in one/few locations along the entire gage length, while wet samples show failure and separation mechanisms in many locations throughout the sample, which indicates that water has penetrated and weakened the matrix and fiber interface in addition to possible plasticizing effects of diffused sea water on the resin matrix itself. However a more detailed analysis of this observation is currently ongoing.

Figure 9: Neutron tomographic reconstructions of dry and wet specimen at two loading conditions (S1 and S4). Top Images resolve vinyl ester resin vs *12k T700* fiber bundles. Images on bottom show CF/VE facing front and side view.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study showed that the specimen size effect of fiber and matrix dominated CF/VE on their mechanical properties is not significant. This is an important finding to extend results from laboratory testing for application to design large polymer composite based marine sandwich structures. A combination of obtaining surface deformations from 3-D Digital Imaging Correlation technique with 3-D Non-Invasive Damage diagnostics using x-ray and neutron imaging is a powerful approach to study deformation behavior of complex multi-phase materials under in situ and extreme environmental conditions. DIC results showed that fiber dominated CF/VE failure was caused by stress localizations distributed along the deforming specimen gage length, leading to an abrupt failure. However, matrix dominated CF/VE was mainly due to large accumulation of strain in a narrow zone, leading to failure. In situ loading with the demonstrated three dimensional characterization techniques enable to perform micro-mechanical assessment of damage in carbon composites, and damage evolution in extreme environment.

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